

Review Article

Christ Metaphorical use of Salt and Light in Matthew 5:13-16 as the Impetus for the Contributions of Theological Education in Transforming the World

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Abstract

In time past, one of the problems of the Church was the belief that the world is so corrupt and firmly in the hands of the evil ones that there is virtually no point of contact between Christians and the world. The Church was seen as having no business in interfering in worldly matters. The world is doomed and must be left as it is for its merited destruction. However, a reflection on the teaching of Christ in Matthew 5: 13-16 has opened the eyes of the Church that the purpose of her calling is not to isolate herself from the world but to transform it. The understanding of this teaching has been the driven force for the Church in transforming the world. Theological Education is one of the most vibrant and dynamic tools the church has been using in transforming the world. By taking into account the political, economic, Education, social and religious challenges across the globe in her curriculum, theological institutions have brought the coveted change into the world. Its impact is now highly felt in all the facet of life. This includes taking the right steps in solving gender and racial discriminations, playing an active role in the fight against HIV and AIDS, giving the adequate information needed to fight against global warming and depletion of natural resources, developing a theology of liberation for the oppressed and the poor. The quest for transforming the world in the light of Jesus teaching in Matthew 5: 13-16 has made theological institutions to take into account political, economic, social and religious problems that are troubling the peace of the world in their theological programmes. The improvement made has made theological education to bring the needed salt and light for transforming the disturbed and destabilised peace of the world.

Keywords: Church, theological education, Christ, world, bible

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Introduction

Benedict (2011) defines education as the complex of the process of socialization that would aid any person in holistic development and wholesome existence from the cradle to the grave. From this definition, one could see that education is a lifetime process and is a weapon for growth, continuity and survival in any society (Adetoye, 2014). It is a means by which vital life experiences and values that are passed from one generation to another are preserved. Education is also a universal phenomenon that takes place at everywhere in the world. This means that the term 'education' is not a strange phenomenon. It is a global concept. It describes the total process of individual learning by which knowledge is impacted, valuable skills developed and faculties trained.

Education is important in the sense that it gives man knowledge of the entire world, makes him capable of interpreting things rightly, and cultivates him into a mature person that is capable of planning for his future and taking the right decision in life. It forms a support system for individuals to excel in life. Considering the place of education in bringing change into the world, Ango (2012) opines that the future of any nation is safe in the hands of educated men and women. This shows that a society that its affairs are not directed by the educated men and women is at the risk of having a bleak future.

Most simply put, theology is the study of God. The term theology comes from the Greek word *θεος* which means God and *-ology* which is from the Greek word *λογος* meaning 'word.' Theology this implies words about God or the study of God. Webster (2016) defines it as the science of God or of religion; the science which treats of the existence, character and attributes of God, his laws and government, the doctrines that man is to believe and the duties that he is to practice. From this definition, one could deduce that theology entails relating to God and his universe rightly or according to His will. It could also be seen as the science of Christian faith and life. Theology is the systematic and rational study of religion, its influences and truths. It is the science of things divine. It could also be defined as the study which, through participation in and reflection on religious faith, seeks to express the content of this faith in the clearest and most consistent language available (Macquarrie, 1986).

Patton (2005) defines theology as a set of intellectual and emotional commitments, justified or not, about God and man which dictate one's beliefs and actions. Following

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Patton definition, it could be seen that wrong theology always leads to wrong behavior. In other words, if one is not having the right perspective of God and His universe, it would affect his behaviour towards God, nature, and his fellow human beings. It means that there is a need to have a real perception of God and man for one's theology to be relevant. From the above definitions, one could infer that theology proceeds from 'religious faith.' Put differently; theology is not just the study of religion; rather it is the study of religion from the perspective of faith. It also reveals that theology is not relevant if it does not solve human problems. A relevant theology is the one that seeks to address human problems from a biblical perspective. A theology that does not solve human problems nor improve man's condition is a dead theology.

Theological Education

Theological Education means teaching the doctrinal truth of the Bible formally and informally with the goal of helping individuals to live a godly life that pleases both God and fellow human beings. Baba (2012) defines theological education as the study of religious faith, practice and experience of spirituality as taught in the Bible. From this definition, it could be deduced that theological education revolves around on the word of God as presented in the Scripture. In the words of Awoniyi (2009), theological education is an aspect of training that prepares individuals to be fulfilled and relevant in the Christian ministry. It means that theological education is geared towards the production of people who are committed to the propagation of the gospel of Christ as well as actualizing the ideals of Christianity contained in the Bible. Ilori (2004) sees it as an avenue for the provision of the right type of values and attitude that will rid the society of its social evils and bring about a mature and disciplined individual who would place God above other considerations. This definition shows that theological education is a tool for transforming the society morally. Wentz defines Theological Education as the preparation of the professional men and women of the ministry for the Christian Churches (Wentz, 1977). Interpreting Wentz definition of Theological Education, theological education is limited to certain people that are specifically trained for various ministries in the Church. Theological Education is broader in scope than the way Wentz has viewed it. It is not limited to the Church alone as the trained in the theological institutions cannot work in isolation. The purpose of their training is not limited to how they can be useful to the church alone but the world in general. Moreover, it is not only Christianity as a religion that emphasizes theological education, but other religions in the world also emphasise the importance of Theological Education to its adherents.

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Adekunle (2011) defines Theological Education as an effort to train and improve a person's faculties, judgment, skill, and competence through exposure to the revealed truth of God systematically outlined and laid out in the Bible, nature, history and other areas of human life. Interpreting Dada's definition, it could be deduced that Theological Education helps man to understand God. This understanding helps man to say yes when God says yes and says no when God says no. His definition also reveals that the source of Theological Education is not limited to the Bible alone. One could have theological knowledge through other means like experience and nature itself.

From the various examined definitions of Theological Education, it is evident that Theological Education is not only a field of study but a way of life that provides the necessary tools for a successful, meaningful and godly living. It exposes individual to the broad knowledge of God in a formal setting with the aim of enabling the individual to learn, understand and practice what he has been taught in a way that others would be influenced to act same. Moreover, it is reasonable to assert that theological education helps the Christians not only to understand and interpret their faith rightly but also enable them to articulate such faith and share it with others through the proclamation of the gospel and godly living. Theological education is also not only Christian affairs. Every religion has its theology. Since all religions advocate for good moral in the society, Theological Education, therefore, helps greatly in character development and spiritual formation of the people in the world. This consequently brings out the positive change demanded from all the individuals in the society.

It is also necessary to point out the fact that the scope of Theological Education goes beyond preparing leaders for ministerial assignment; rather it extends to administering the knowledge to build lives, effect changes in behavioural, emotional, mental and psychological disorder or abnormalities that result to problems. Other areas of its operation include checking or resolving imbalances and bringing rightness into human senses for right living in the human community. Steven (2007) opines that the primary task of Theological Education is to shape the lives of the Christians so that God can use them as leaders and influencers for the good of humanity. Pointing out the place of Theological Education in bringing solution to the perennial problems in the world, Collins (1988) asserts:

Most continuing crises in the world are caused by factors that becloud the human mind, awareness, and understanding. Some problems encounter

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either individually or collectively emanate from self-centeredness, impediments to life goals, disorganization, or disruption. Character and various vices like 'mate-beating, father-daughter incest, fear, confusion, threats of suicide, homosexuality, alcoholism, drug abuse, depression, anxiety, guilt, family problems and a host of other problems are other aspects of life where people have problems. All these problems could be averted if people are exposed to Theological Education (p.15).

From the above assertion, Theological Education can be said to be the external factor that significantly determines the behaviour of a person and also plays a complementary role in the realisation of high goals at both individual and social levels. It could also be said that the impact of Theological Education in the life of a person stems out of significant changes manifesting positively in development, growth, and intellect. It shows pragmatic re-orientation from the parameters of ignorance, darkness, and dullness of life matters into better awareness, better understanding, and better performance.

After examining the meaning of theology, education, theological education and its importance, attention would now be shifted to Christ metaphorical use of salt and light in Matthew 5: 13-16. The application of this text has been the driving force behind the Church's using of theological education as a tool for transforming the world

The Sermon on the Mount

The first century Judea was filled with many problems. The land was occupied by a tyrannical military government. It was a world of absolute rulers, the antithesis of democracy. It was a world of persecution from the Romans. Taxes consumed a third of their income. Radical prejudice was prevalent to the point that men no longer knew who their neighbor was (Luke 10:25-36). Slavery was rampant. In response to this sad situation, many answers were given by sects of the Jews. The zealots, like the terrorists of today, tried to bring the demanded transformation through military might. The Sadducees tried to survive by compromising with the Roman Government. The Essenes, having lost the hope of bringing the Reformation they long awaited for, they decided to live an isolated life. To the Pharisees, the way to put out the transformation was by living a clean, ritually pure life as defined by the law and the tradition of the Rabbis. An outward expression and display not upon inner holiness (Padfield, 1982).

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In the midst of these various responses, Jesus came up and delivered the Sermon on the Mount in the second year of his ministry, when he was drawing near the peak of his popularity. With the sermon, Jesus rejected the doctrines of the sects in Judea as the means to the needed transformation. It worth noting that the main theme of the sermon is true righteousness which is not an artificial, external righteousness based on a law which the Pharisees were concerned with. However, the one that begins internally, in the heart, the one that forces one to move beyond the stage of regret to that of a changed life. The Sermon on the Mount is probably the best known, but least understood and least followed, of all the teachings of Christ (Wiersbe, 1989). Green (1988) sees it as the supreme jewel in the crown of Jesus' teaching. Boice (1972) opines that the sermon is important to believers not only because it shows the absolute necessity of the new birth and that it points to Christ but that it also indicates the way of blessings for Christians and the way to please the heavenly Father. The sermon also reveals what true righteousness is. There are different views on the Sermon on the Mount. Some see the sermon as the ways men will live when Jesus returns to reign. The interpretation of this view is that the Sermon is not applicable to the present age but the age to come. The weakness of this view is that it is being used to excuse behavior and attitudes that fall far short of the standard Jesus expressed. Another view suggests that the sermon is addressed primarily to the Church. This view fails to recognize the fact that at this stage of Jesus ministry, Israel and not the Church, was central (Richards, 1987). Another view opines that the sermon is God's plan for of salvation, that is, if anyone ever hopes to go to heaven, he must obey these rules. It would be a balanced view to see the Sermon as:

A detailed exposition for Jesus hearers of what repentance involves

The life in the eschatological Kingdom

Standards that reflect God's character and His will

Viewing the Sermon in these perspectives will make the sermon relevant for the present age as well as the future kingdom. To Wiersbe (1989), the Beatitudes reveals the four-dimensional attitudes required of man which are: his attitude toward himself (Matthew 5:3), sins (Matthew 5: 4-6), the Lord (Matthew 5: 7-9), and the world (Matthew 5: 10-16). Jesus the point is that the values of this world do not lead to blessing. Instead, blessing

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comes through living by values which the world despises, but which God holds dear. It is with this background that attention of this work would be turned to Matthew 5:13-16, the text that centered on the fourth dimension of Christ's sermon which is on the attitude required of a believer towards the world. In order to discover the meaning of the salt metaphor as used by Christ in this passage, there is a need to understand the function of salt as it would be understood by Jesus' original first-century audience. To achieve this purpose, attention of this work would be shifted to the place of salt in antiquity and the Scriptures as a whole.

Salt in Antiquity

In antiquity, Homer has been said to call salt a divine substance. Plato was also to have described it as being especially dear to the gods (Mckenze, 1995). Salt was a valuable commodity in the ancient world. People traded with it, as one trades with gold and stock. Salt also served a very useful purpose in hot climates before the invention of electricity and refrigeration. Salt not only gave food flavour, but it also preserved meat from spoiling. Taxes on salt have secured empires and inspired a revolution. The Romans appear to have esteemed salt highly. Its army, for a time, was even paid in salt. This is the origin of the word "salary" and the expressions "worth his salt" and "earning his salt." "He is not worth his salt." That is the origin of the expression, "worth his salt." (Michael, 2008). Based on this, it is saved to say that the salt metaphor as used by Christ carries a general idea of value. Disciples, therefore, add value to the world in a broad sense. In fact, the Latin word *sal* became the French word *solde*, meaning "pay," and has come down from the word "soldier." The first of the great Roman roads was the Via Salaria, the Salt Road. The Romans used to salt their greens, which is the origin of the word "salad," salted (Akzo, 2014).

Salt in Biblical Perspective

The main source of salt in the area of Palestine was the area of the Dead Sea, especially the massive, about seven miles long, salt cliffs of Jebel Usdum (Easton, 1987). The Hebrew people harvested salt by pouring sea water into pits and letting the water evaporate until the only salt was left. They used the mineral for seasoning and as a preservative. Also, salt was used to disinfect wounds (Hirst, 2011). In 2 Chron 13:5 King Abijah referred to God's covenant promise to David that he will not lack a man to sit on Israel's throne as a Salt covenant - that is a covenant that can never be broken. Salt was widely and variably used as a symbol and sacred sign in ancient Israel. Numbers 18:19 and 2 Chronicles 13:5

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illustrate salt as a covenant of friendship. In cultures throughout the region, the eating of salt is a sign of friendship. Salt land is a metaphorical name for a desolate no man's land, as attested in Psalms 107:34, Job 39:6, and Jeremiah 17:6. The land of defeated cities was salted to consecrate them to a god and curse their re-population, as illustrated in Judges 9:45.

Moreover, the use of salt is indispensable in Israel's rituals. Just as salt was necessary for meals, so it was essential to the sacrifice, the "food of God" (Lev. 21: 22). The Law expressly says: "Every oblation of thy meal-offering shalt thou season with salt." This prescription referred not only to the meal-offering but also to the burnt offering of animals, as appears from Ezek. 43: 24. Salt was also used in the preparation of the showbread Lev. 24: 7 and of incense. Great quantities of salt (Ezra 6: 9, 7: 22) were therefore required in the Temple service (Linda, 2016).

The medical properties of salt also seem to have been known to the Israelites at an early date. Newborn infants were rubbed with it (Ezek.16. 4). The significance of rubbing a newborn with salt is to indicate that the child would be raised to have integrity and be truthful always. The curative and sanitary properties of salt are probably referred to in the story related in 2 Kings 2:19ff according to which Elisha "heals" the poisonous spring near Jericho by using salt (Robert, 2013).

The significance of salt among the Jews is particularly pointed out by the Rabbis. They interpret the words "a covenant of salt" (Num. 18: 19) as meaning that salt was used by God on occasion in question to signify that it should never be lacking from sacrifices. Thus, although it appears from Lev. 2: 13 that salt was required for meal-offerings only, the Rabbis concluded that just as none of the sacrifices could be offered without priests, so they could not be offered without salt (Gwamma, 2012). The salt which belonged to the Temple for sacrificial purposes could be used by the priests when they ate their portion of the sacrifices, but not otherwise. After the destruction of the Temple, the table set for a meal was considered as an altar. The Rabbis recommended that salt is put upon it and that blessing should not be recited without salt. The necessity for the presence of salt is indicated by the fact that when the bread is of inferior quality a man may ask for salt between the recitation of the blessing and the partaking of the bread, while one is not allowed to utter a single word for other reasons. However, when the bread is of good

quality, although salt should have been put on the table, yet, if it is missing, one may not interrupt by asking for it between the blessing and eating.

The Rabbis also likened the Torah to salt; for as the world could not do without salt, neither could it do without the Torah. Salt is not considered by the Rabbis as food; thus when one makes a vow to abstain from the food he may eat salt. Salt is also one of the things that must not be used in excess (Linda, 2016). The Rabbis recognized in different salt properties owing to which it is prominent in the ritual code. The most important one is its decomposing action on the blood, and therefore its use was recommended by the Rabbis for draining the blood from meat. Blood cannot be thoroughly extracted from meat unless the latter is well salted.

Exegetical Analysis of Matthew 5:13-16

13. ὑμεῖς ἐστε τὸ ἅλας τῆς γῆς· ἐὰν δὲ τὸ ἅλας μωρανθῇ, ἐν τίνι ἀλισθήσεται; εἰς οὐδὲν ἰσχύει ἔτι εἰ μὴ βληθὲν ἔξω καταπατεῖσθαι ὑπὸ τῶν ἀνθρώπων. 14. ὑμεῖς ἐστε τὸ φῶς τοῦ κόσμου. οὐ δύναται πόλις κρυβῆναι ἐπάνω ὄρους κειμένη· 15. οὐδὲ καίουσιν λύχνον καὶ τιθέασιν αὐτὸν ὑπὸ τὸν μῶδιον ἀλλ’ ἐπὶ τὴν λυχνίαν, καὶ λάμπει πᾶσιν τοῖς ἐν τῇ οἰκίᾳ. 16. οὕτως λαμψάτω τὸ φῶς ὑμῶν ἔμπροσθεν τῶν ἀνθρώπων, ὅπως ἴδωσιν ὑμῶν τὰ καλὰ ἔργα καὶ δοξάσωσιν τὸν πατέρα ὑμῶν τὸν ἐν τοῖς οὐρανοῖς.

13. ‘You are the salt of the earth; but if salt has lost its taste, how can its saltiness be restored? It is no longer good for anything, but is thrown out and trampled underfoot.

14. ‘You are the light of the world. A city built on a hill cannot be hidden. 15. No one after lighting a lamp puts it under a bushel basket, but on the lampstand, and it gives light to all in the house. 16. ‘In the same way, let your light shine before others, so that they may see your good works and give glory to your Father in heaven (RSV).

The Beatitudes are followed by a couplet of short metaphoric parables of salt and light that Jesus used to expand upon the role of the μακαριοὶ in the world (5:13-16) (Davies, 1989). As in the case of other parables, Jesus used here an illustration understandable to the first-century audience. Salt and light were common elements in antiquity. Pliny the Elder (AD 23-79), a contemporary of Jesus, stated: “For the whole body nothing is more beneficial than salt and the sun (). It appears that these couplet parables of salt and light in the Sermon on the Mount function as a dual-directional passage concluding the Beatitudes and, at the same time, introducing the rest of the Discourse.

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The use of 'salt and light' metaphors finds parallels in Mark 9:50 and Luke 14:34 which some scholars speculate as for the 'Q' document. Matthew's account differs slightly from that of Luke and Mark. Matthew 5:13-16 emphasises that disciples must be a blessing and a preservative in the world, Mark 9:50 emphasises that they must be faithful to their covenant relationship with one another. Luke emphasizes that they must maintain allegiance to Christ. One view is that the Salt and Light as used in Matthew 5: 13-16 refers to a duality of roles in the disciples to be like a light from a city, viewable from all over the world, and to be spread out as salt is: to congregate and spread.

"You are the Salt of the Earth" (5:13)

In the first metaphoric parable, Jesus likens the disciples to salt; "you are the salt of the earth" ὑμεῖς ἐστε τὸ ἅλας τῆς γῆς. The emphatic pronoun ὑμεῖς meaning literally "you yourselves [are salt]" refers to "you are blessed/happy" in verse 11. It suggests that those who are the salt of the earth, as well as the light of the world, are the μακαριοὶ of the Beatitudes. In comparing his disciples to salt, Jesus referred to the mineral known today as sodium chloride. Salt was a necessity of life in Palestine, as in the rest of the ancient world. The book of Sirach lists it as one of the core needs of life (39:26). The Dead Sea was a major source of salt in Palestine. However, Dead Sea salt was impure, mixed with gypsum and other minerals producing an alkaline or bitter taste, for which reason the people of Palestine often purchased salt of superior quality from the traders in the North. The word salt ἅλας occurs in six passages of the New Testament of which five times in the Synoptics in the sayings of Jesus (Matt. 5:13; Mark 9:50; Luke 14:34). The verb ἀλιζῶ simply means "to salt" or "to season with salt." Salt is used exclusively in a figurative sense, taken, however from domestic consumption. Because of the extensive use of salt in the ancient world, commentators have made many suggestions of its metaphoric meaning in Matthew 5:13.

A debatable issue among commentators regards the rhetorical question made by Jesus: "If the salt has become tasteless, how can it be made salty?" Did Jesus mean that salt could lose its tasty effect? Some commentators believe that this loss of saltiness refers most likely to the aforementioned poor quality of the Dead Sea salt (Hillyer, 1986). Because of its impurity, it has been argued that the salt in Palestine could lose its distinctive flavour. In actuality, however, salt is a stable compound and, as such, it does not lose its saltiness. That such was the understanding among first-century Jews may be

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seen from a story attributed to Rabbi Joshua ben Haninia (A.D. first cent.). When asked if salt loses its flavor, the rabbi responded: "Does the mule bear young?" The point the rabbi tried to make was that salt could not lose its flavor as much as a sterile mule could not produce an offspring (Craig, 2009). It seems that the question of whether salt can lose its saltiness is beside the point Jesus tried to make to the disciples. As France (1985) observes, Jesus was not teaching his disciples about chemistry or chemical processes; instead, he coined a proverbial illustration to make a theological point. Real salt does not lose its saltiness. Salt without saltiness is not salt, and as such, it has no value and use; "so does a professed disciple who lacks genuine commitment' (Craig, 2009).

Matthew, Mark and Luke accord in the discussion of salt "that has lost its taste." This is a reference to salt that is contaminated with other minerals, causing a weakness in flavor or a bland unpleasant taste. It may be a symbolic reference to the possibility of abandoning or deviating from the gospel, especially due to the adulteration of its teachings. Another interpretation is that in a world filled with sin and deceit, it is possible for one to become contaminated and thus unsuccessful at being an effective disciple. Therefore, this verse serves as a warning for disciples to be on their guard; to be in the world, but not of the world.

The verb for "tasteless" used in Matthew 5:13 mean literally "become foolish' $\mu\omega\rho\alpha\nu\tau\eta$, so also in Luke 14:34). Thus, a point Jesus makes is that, as it is impossible for salt to lose its saltiness, so the $\mu\alpha\kappa\alpha\rho\iota\omicron\iota$ referred to in the Beatitudes cannot lose their spiritual flavor as long as they are the followers of Christ. However, salt that (hypothetically) loses its saltiness would be good for nothing. This notion sets the disciples in contrast to the Scribes and the Pharisees.

Craig thus rightly observes that the first-century listeners would have quickly grasped the point Jesus tried to make to the disciples. As salt gives flavor to food, so the disciples are to give flavor to the earth. Salt is supposed to flavor the earth, not earth to the salt. Earth is here a synonym for the world (5:14). The salt mixed in food cannot be seen, only tasted. The most obvious characteristic of salt is that it is different from its locality. The disciples who lose saltiness are of no value any longer.

From the Scriptures, Israel is spoken regarding a light to the nations (Isaiah 60:1-3). It might be the reason why Gundry (1982), affirms that salt was used metaphorically to refer to

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Israel as an agent of purity in the world. The mission of the Servant in Isaiah is portrayed regarding light (Isa. 42:6; 49:6), which was in the New Testament fulfilled in the ministry of Jesus (Matt. 4:16; Luke 2:32; John 8:12). Paul also often uses the light metaphor for the gospel (2 Cor. 4:6; Eph. 5:8; Phil 2:15). Here, in Matthew 5:14-16, Jesus exhorts the disciples to be a shining light to the world, just as he is the light of the world. It appears that the structure of the light metaphor (5:14-16) is comparably similar to the salt metaphor (5:13):

You are the salt of the earth (The salt must not lose its flavor).
You are the light of the world (The light cannot be hidden)

This comparison shows that the two metaphors are complementary to each other. In Matthew 5:14-16, Jesus reiterates the point made in the metaphor of “the salt of the earth” (v. 13). Just as salt provides taste and transforms food, so the lamp provides “light to all who are in the house.” Also, as it is impossible for salt to lose its saltiness, so it is impossible to hide or conceal the light— like a city on a hill: “The city on the hill cannot be hidden” (v. 14).

Jesus further enhances the metaphor of light with another proverbial saying: “Nobody lights a lamp and puts it under a basket but on a lampstand” (5:15). Here, Jesus referred to a typical one-room Palestinian house. A lamp *λυχνος* was a small clay vessel with a spout on one end in which a wick was set. It was filled with oil and placed on a lamp stand or a unique hole in the roomwall to provide illumination in the house. In order to illuminate the house, the light is never covered with a basket. The point Jesus made was that when a person lights a lamp, it is placed on a lamp stand where it produces the most efficient light for every individual in the house. As such light cannot be concealed, so the light of the disciples. Their lives and deeds are visible to the world. “Let your shine before men in such a way that they may see your good works, and glorify your Father who is in heaven” (5:16). The disciples do not generate light; their light is a reflection of their Father who is heaven.

Reflecting on the exegetical analysis of Matthew 5: 13-16, it could be deduced that Jesus clearly used ordinary images, such as salt and light, to convey extraordinary truths. Jesus used the image of salt to describe how his disciples are to live in the world. As salt purifies, preserves, and penetrates, so the disciple must be as salt in the world of human society to purify, preserve, and penetrate that society for the kingdom of God and his

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righteousness and peace. Jesus also used the image of light and a lamp to further his illustration. Lamps in the ancient world served a vital function, much like they do today. They enable people to see and work in the dark and to avoid stumbling. The Jews also understood "light" as an expression of the inner beauty, truth, and goodness of God (Psalm 36:9; Psalm 119:105). Jesus used the image of a lamp to describe how his disciples are to live in the light of his truth and love. Just as natural light illumines the darkness and enables one to see visually, so the light of Christ shines in the hearts of believers and enables them to see the heavenly reality of God's kingdom. God's grace not only illumines the darkness in the world, but it also fills it with spiritual light, joy, and peace.

Against the call for isolation as some people wrongly conceived, Christian's mission is to be light-bearers of Christ so that others may see the truth of the gospel and be freed from the blindness of sin and deception that permeates the world today. The man is obviously surrounded by his moral and spiritual darkness. He is blind spiritually. The Christians in the world are to be spectacles to the world by their good works in the society both in teaching and in practice. It is by doing this that the world can be transformed into a place where peace and tranquility reign.

Theological Education as the 'Salt and Light' in Transforming the World

Having looked into the exegetical analysis of Jesus uses of salt and light as to mean that the followers of Christ must be transforming agents in the world, how theological education has been functioning as a tool for transformation in the world is the next focus of this study.

Teaching Christian Ethics in the Theological Institutions

Christian ethics, seen from a holistic perspective, has unique nature, which stands in sharp contrast with the anthropocentric view of goodness developed by the Greek tradition. The concept of good is theological in Christian ethics and is widely taught in all the theological institutions in the world. It is redemptive in nature as it is designed to save humanity from moral depravity. It imposes obligations on every person to do what is morally right to others. As rightly noted by Obaje (2002), theological education transforms individual based on God's given moral standard as stipulated in the Scripture. As usually taught in theological institutions, an inbuilt power to transform both the individual and the society is portrayed by such virtues as truthfulness, courage, justice,

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compassion, love, punctuality to work among others. Teaching Christian ethics enables the students to maintain the virtuous action, emotion and thought despite pressures to do otherwise.

Good moral is also mandatory for all theological students. More so, good moral is not optional for any person created by God. The essence of good moral is to ensure, guarantee and promote a healthy balance atmosphere among all human beings in all places, at all times and all levels. Obaje (2002) identifies these levels to be four: God-ward, nation-ward, neighbor-ward, and self-ward. It implies that any human behavior or moral action that does not enjoy equilibrium on all these 'wards' is morally defective and bound to be abnormal. Thus teaching good moral in theological institutions has helped in the sustaining wholesome balance of moral integrity in tune with God-given nature and purpose in life not only among the Christians alone but also in the world as the students interact with the world and influenced people to do what is good to others. Theological Education has also helped in the area of writings and publishing of books that transformed lives.

Establishment of various Theological Institutions for Training the World Leaders

Theological Institutions have become the backbone of evangelism in the world. In recognition of the importance of Theological Education in the world, some universities and other tertiary institutions have established departments of theology and religious studies which cater specifically for theological and religious education. Some of the students who have graduated in such institutions serve either as full-time or part-time ministers in their churches. The need for well-trained ministers has necessitated the ecumenical cooperation of the churches in the world. In this regard especially after the world wars, attempts have been made to embark on joint theological training. In recent years, ecumenical efforts in Theological Education have led to establishing and theological colleges. Though most of these theological institutions place a great emphasis on theological training of their ministers, yet their emphasis is not only to train church ministers who can preach and evangelise. Nevertheless, it also produces ministers who can easily address and respond to the modern day issues that are affecting the world populace like gender discrimination, poverty, HIV/AIDS, wars, child abuse among others.

Theological institutions, from time immemorial, have been in the vanguard of ministerial training personnel, teachers of high repute and men and women of the high educational profile. Some of these people who have been trained in the theological institutions have served as think tanks for nations in the world. Some of them have become leaders in the society, while others are in the academics. Being institutions of higher education themselves, they have also, through this major contribution, provided the opportunity for service for some of their products who excelled in their particular areas. By so doing, they have helped to place bread on the tables of some highly trained personnel who would, otherwise, have been in the unemployment market. Theological Education has helped the Church in preserving its tradition and also in providing adequate theological education to the respective denominational leaders.

Addressing the Problem of Gender Discrimination

One of the problems that are affecting the world the progress of the world today is gender discrimination. The Bible has been view by many female theologians as too patriarchal. The theology of the Church was male dominated. God is perceived as male, and as a matter of fact, Christ was a man and not a woman likewise all Christ's disciples. Church ministry as a concept of male priesthood was taken as a God-given and unchangeable in practically most Churches as if it were by divine decree from the time of creation. To buttress the point of gender discrimination, for example in Africa, many missionaries were accompanied by their wives and other women missionaries as doctors, nurses, and teachers; their presence, however, was hardly registered, and if even registered, it would not be on same par with that of male counterparts. This shows that male dominated the missionary field at the expense of female missionaries whose presence was quite often overshadowed by men. The implication of this attitude excluded the women not only from ministering the Lord fully to the world but also turn them to mere spectators and not active participants in transforming the world. The comment of Buhari, the president of Nigeria in response to his wife displeasure concerning his administrative policies is surprising. This comment, that his wife has no right to voice out her view concerning what is going on in Nigeria politics because she only belongs to 'the kitchen and the other room,' confirms the discrimination of the women even by some world leaders.

As the Church progresses in evangelizing the world to do the will of God to restore peace and promote unity in the world, Theological institutions have recognized the injustices that have been perpetrated against the women in the society. This is a disguise of religion

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by excluding the women from playing active role in the Church and the society. The Church has become aware of the important role that women play in the Church and the society (Jegede, 2012). Politically, some of the women have assumed the position of president, minister, senator head of the tertiary institution, speaker of the house of parliament, the prime minister, soldier, among others. The just concluded election for one of the most glorified seats in the world if not the most glorified seat between Hillary Clinton and Donald Trump in the United States of America is living evidence that women can no longer be relegated in politics and also in the quest of changing the world for better.

Based on this wind of change, most theological institutions have integrated into their curriculum gender studies that are designed to promote women's issues. Theological reflection on the position and role of women in the church and the society is now firmly entrenched in the curriculum in many university departments of theology and religious institutions. All forms of gender discrimination are now condemned in most of the theological institutions. Emphasis is now placed on promoting equal participation of both men and women in the ministry of the church. Most theological institutions now include women in their theological programmes, who eventually become pastors, bishops, prophetess and Church leaders. This is intended to empower women not only in the church but also to enable them to be agents of change in the society for the common good of all.

Condemning Racial Discrimination

Theological education has contributed immensely to the democratization of some countries through its development of liberation theology and theology of democratization and equality of all races in the world. Up until the time of independence of some African countries, the African Church, for example, was characterized by an uncompromising stand against African people and culture by the Western missionaries. Her culture was considered evil and anti-Christian. African songs, language, dressings were seen as inferior to the colonial masters. Africans despite having the needed qualifications to lead the Church were not permitted to do so. African world-view was not perfectly respected. This negative approach to African culture resulted in resentment towards Christianity at the initial stage while some broke away from the mainline Churches and formed their churches which have come to be known as African Indigenous Churches.

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Due to the contributions of various theologians, theological education has contributed to the democratization process of many countries, especially in Africa. A good example was that of the apartheid period in South Africa when many lost their birth right through land possession, racial segregation and discrimination in Churches, employment, education, and politics. African theologians then used Latin American Liberation Theology and North American Black Theology to articulate their views on the urgency for a new dispensation which finally yielded the needed fruit. These theologies emphasized and still emphasise God's preferential love for the poor, his solidarity with the oppressed, salvation as holistic liberation and egalitarian society (Migliore, 2004). These theologies equipped theological students with the ideological tools needed to fight against corruption, and other oppressors in the form of religious protests through academic writings. Sometheological and religious institutions have now become a bastion of the new way of thinking in liberating the society from the oppressors.

Prompt Attention to Health Challenges

One of the health problems that the world is facing today is that of the HIV/AIDS pandemic. The epidemic has left behind millions of orphans who have lost their parents to the disease (Oderinde, 2004). In the past decades, HIV/AIDS has been the focus of theological reflection. One of the obstacles in preventing the spread of the disease is a stigma. This is because stigma prevents people from going for voluntary testing and counseling, and declaring their HIV status. As a result, they pass on the virus to other ignorantly. Consequently, AIDS has become a silent killer with funeral processions taking place every day to the point that many families have been impoverished because of the funeral cost (Amanze, 2007).

At the beginning of this challenge, many churches were biased, saying that the epidemic is a punishment from God. Today, there has been a paradigm of change in the theological reflection of the churches concerning the outbreak. Many theological institutions have now developed 'theologies of hope' as against 'theologies of doom and retribution. This theology of hope has helped a lot in solving the problem of stigmatization and consequently brought a significant change in the rate of infection of the disease in the world. Moreover, HIV/AIDS has been included in the curriculum of most of the theological institutions. Students are now being taught how HIV is being contracted, transmitted and how it can be prevented. Personnel are also trained to offer counseling services to people who have been infected and affected by the epidemic. Young people

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are also encouraged to abstain from pre-marital sex. This is done using organized seminars, workshops, and conferences run by the various theological institutions. It is hoped through all these efforts and the unrelenting efforts of the scientists, the world would produce an HIV/AIDS-free generation in the nearest future.

Preservation of the Environment

The problem of global warming and preservation of the environment is no longer a problem

That is left to the scientists alone to solve. The need to preserve natural resources and protect the environment from degradation is now one of the top priorities in theological education. In its contribution to the preservation of natural resources for future generations, environmental issues have now been integrated into the various theological institution's curriculum. The problems of erosion, over-grazing, global warming, oil spillage, air pollution, deforestation, destruction of wildlife, urban and rural pollution are now discussed for the purpose of creating awareness of the people in the society regarding the abuses of the natural resources and consequences. To make this effective, workshops and conferences are regularly organized to conscientious the trained people of God to conserve and preserve the natural resources and also teach others to do so. This effort has been helpful to the society in bringing to minimal the rate of destruction and abuse of natural resources among the various members of the society.

The main issue on ecology today is that humans have distorted the God-made and given nature. As rightly observed by Adejuwon (2009), the healthy relationship between humans, animals, plants and non-living things within the given environment, has been marred by abuse and exploitation by humanity against the other creations. The main cause of this could be traced to the misinterpretation of Genesis 1:28. Instead of seeing the passage as a command to care for God's creation, man has chosen to stress 'fill the earth and subdue it' to legitimize abuse, misuse, and exploitations of what God created. This misinterpretation of the word of God has reduced nature to a mere object of human use. In response to this reality, theological education has established a new understanding and a call for a new relationship with nature. This step has started to help man to manage and care for the environment positively.

At no time has the Church been more interested in environmental ethics than now. The general notion that ecological concerns are rarely prominent in theory or practices of the Church is now becoming history. Tropical deforestation aggravated with the booming charcoal industry, importation of used items, which have become junks constituting an environmental nuisance to man's environment, global warming and erosion which has deeply eaten into the land are serious threats to climatic conditions and agricultural production all over the world. Since the 1983 assembly of the World Church Council (WCC) in Vancouver, the call to the Church and all students in the theological institutions to engage in a concrete process of mutual commitment to justice, peace and integrity of creation, has produced greater awareness and efforts to curb environmental crises (Amanze, 2009)

Peaceful Coexistence in the Multi- Faith Society

In the past theological institutions emphasized the exclusive nature of Christianity at the expense of other faiths. Today, this attitude has changed in the world. The reality of the existence of other religions competing with Christianity and the need to live peaceably with the adherents of these world religions has called for a move towards a multi-faith approach to theological education.

To forge peaceful coexistence, a course like Inter-Religious Dialogue has been introduced in the curriculum of most theological institutions and universities. This has helped to promote religious tolerance in the society. Religious exclusivism is now discouraged for religious pluralism. Theological curriculum includes not only the study of Christianity but also of other religions. The syllabus normally covers the life of the founders of the different religions, major beliefs, rituals, and practices. It is helping in understanding the tenets of other faiths and the best way to witness unto them without causing the religious crisis.

Socio-Economic Development

Ronald, (2004) has defined social actions as that set of activities whose primary goal is improving the physical, social, economic and political well-being of people through relief, development, and structural change. To interpreting this, purpose of social action then is to prevent starvation, empower the poor and improving social structures so that the persons created in God's image can enjoy more of the wholeness the Creator intended for them. Stott (2005) sees Christians as salt and light of the world through their social

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responsibilities. For example, missionary encounter in Africa came with the gospel and social action. The establishment of Schools, hospitals, and other infrastructural developments was a major transformation force and tool in the socio-religious lives of the people. It was one of the major attractions to Christianity in Africa. Education which was allied to Christianity brought tremendous transformation of lives in individuals, families, and communities in Africa which left lasting impressions and legacies, some of which have endured till date. In the words of Harold (1952) 'when missionaries came to Africa, it was like one lighting a torchlight in a darkroom.'

In recent times, theological education has taken into consideration the problem concerning the socio-economic development of the world. It is widely known that due to corruption, bad leaders, wars, disaster, drought, terrorism, civil unrest and many others, poverty and immorality has destroyed to a great extent the development of the society and its peace. To bring the positive change needed in the society, the theological institutions advocate and insist that the development of the society be through the empowerment of the members of the society and equip them with skills to deal with their situations effectively. Students of the theological institutions are taught to be the catalyst for a change by engaging themselves in development work and also to teach members of the society to do so. To this effect, workshops, seminars, and conferences are organized to conscientise both the society and the students to engage themselves in developmental programmes. The church is also helping through the creation of jobs to the masses by establishing various institutions of learning, subsidizing the school fees of the students, establishing income generated companies to create employment for the masses. A loan with little or no interest is also given to the needy sometimes to start their self-own business.

Addressing the Problem of High Rate of Crimes in the World

Theological Education has continued to be an indispensable tool in solving various crises in the society. Regarding the socio-economic crises that permeate the world, all the efforts of the government that do not employ theological education in fighting corruption and other social ills defy solution because the right instrument to challenge the monster is not employed. Theological education has been a valuable tool, especially when blended with secular education in refining the polluted mind of man. It has helped greatly in influencing the minds of people in government and the private sector. The education that

is wrapped with the power of the word (theology) always tackled socio-economic and political crises meaningfully, adequately and efficiently.

Conclusion

This paper has looked into the theological institutions as the agents of change and transformation in the society. This work argues that in the past, theological education has contributed negatively to the society through its teaching on particularism of Christianity, justifying the problem of HIV/ AIDS as punishment for man's sexual sin and its patriarchal belief which is anti-women. This has led to religious intolerance and also impacted negatively on the development of the church and the society. Reflecting on the teaching of Christ that believers should be agents of change as revealed in his metaphorical usage of salt and light coupled with the challenging issues facing the world today have made the theological educators to change the course. New theologies like feminist, liberation, ecological theology among others have now emerged to address the challenges that are facing the world. To this effect, theological educators have now contributed immensely to the development of the society economically, socially, morally, educationally and spiritually. Some of the steps taken to bring the positive change include organizing conferences, seminars, workshops and integrating programmes in the curriculum of the theological institutions that address the politics, economic, social, health, moral and religious life of the members of the society.

The effect of this change is noticed in the reduction of the spread of HIV/ AIDS, more involvement of women in the development of the world, religious tolerance, peaceful coexistence between the Christians and the adherents of other world religions and among different races in the world. More so there is now noticeable better management of the natural resources and increase in the economic well-being of the members of the society when one compares the theologies of then theological institutions and curriculum to the present curriculum and theologies at least to an extent.

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